

EVALUATION OF THE COMPOSITION AND STRUCTURE OF INVASIVE PLANTS IN THE WEST SUMATRA CONSERVATION AREA: IMPACT AND MANAGEMENT STRATEGY

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Invasive plant species are plant species, both native and non-native, that colonize or dominate a habitat on a massive scale which can cause ecological, economic and social harm (Permen LHK No. 94, 2016). Invasive foreign plants are known as species that threaten the integrity of natural and semi-natural areas and have a tremendous negative impact on flora and fauna communities. There are at least 1,936 types of foreign plants in Indonesia, some of which have developed into invasiveness and have had a negative impact on several ecosystems (Tjitrosoedirdjo et al. 2016). Research on the composition and structure of invasive plants in West Sumatra conservation areas is important to understand their impact on biodiversity and ecosystem sustainability. Many studies have been conducted on the structure and composition of invasive plants in West Sumatra. However, there are still significant gaps in understanding the ecological interactions of invasive plants with local species and the effectiveness of management strategies. Tjitrosoedirdjo (2005) said that invasive species have now become a threat to the sustainability of biodiversity and native ecosystems. According to Solfiyeni et al., (2016), to optimize the function of conservation areas, effective and targeted management efforts are needed. In their other research, Solfiyeni, Hafizhah, & Winda (2023) emphasized that efforts to preserve biodiversity by establishing conservation areas such as nature reserves do not necessarily make forest areas far from the threat of extinction. One of the most dangerous factors is the presence of invasive foreign plants.

West Sumatra Province has several areas declared as conservation areas, such as nature reserves, national parks and grand forest parks. Several conservation areas in West Sumatra include Maninjau Nature Reserve, Anai Valley Nature Reserve, Kerinci Seblat National Park, Bung Hatta Grand Forest Park, Siberut National Park, Rimbo Panti Nature Reserve, and Bukit Bungkuk Nature Reserve. Sayfulloh et al., (2020) revealed that the presence of invasive alien plants in national parks has been widely reported to cause negative impacts on ecosystems, local biodiversity and even socio-economic and human health in the surrounding areas. Invasive plant species pose a real threat to biodiversity because they can damage forest biodiversity (Master, 2015). Thapa et al., (2018) revealed that invasive plants are also an international problem in biodiversity conservation efforts, where their control and management require enormous costs. Thapa et al. (2018) also added that invasive plants are a serious threat because they can damage native ecosystems and change the nutrient cycle and hydrological cycle.

In research by Solfiyeni et al., (2016) in the Anai Valley Nature Reserve area, West Sumatra, it was found that the invasive plant diversity index value in the area was classified as moderate, namely 2.80. It is highly feared that the diversity of invasive plants could reduce the diversity of living creatures in the Anai Valley Nature Reserve area. In Sahira et al., (2016) invasive foreign plants in the Dr. Forest Park area. Moh. Hatta, which is found at the seedling and understory level, consists of 12 families with 18 species. It is hoped that the research carried out can be used as a source of information about the diversity of invasive alien plant species and as a

consideration in efforts to manage invasive plants. There have been many cases of conservation areas whose diversity and sustainability are threatened due to invasion by invasive plants. As in the research results of Sunaryo et al. (2012), explained that there are three invasive alien plant species, namely *Maesopsis emenii*, *Calliandra callothyrus*, and *Austroepatorium inulaefolium* which threaten the preservation of the ecosystem and the existence of native flora in the Bodogol Resort area, Gunung Gede Pangrango National Park. Sabarno (2002) revealed that the invasion of *Acacia nilotica* in the Savana area of Baluran National Park caused a decrease in the area of savanna, which resulted in changes in the composition, structure and productivity of grass as food for herbivores to become inadequate, so it is feared that the herbivore population in the area will continue to decrease. Solfiyeni et al., (2016) argue that the dominating nature of a particular species can have a negative impact on the ecosystem that that species inhabits.

Inventory and identification of plants in habitats invaded by invasive plants is very necessary for early detection of invasive plant species (Solfiyeni et al., 2022). In research by Solfiyeni et al., (2023) in the Silokek Geopark tourist area, quite a lot of invasive plants were found so that regular monitoring of invasive plants is needed to protect the area from damage. Suri and Solfiyeni (2024) in their research found that the invasive species *Bellucia pentamera* was dominant in the forest in the Kapalo Banda tourist attraction area, where this area is located adjacent to a water source. Dillis et al. (2017) revealed that *B. pentamera* that grows close to rivers will produce twice as many fruit, so this supports the rapid proliferation of *B. pentamera*. As argued by Tustiyani et al., (2019), surrounding environmental conditions can influence the composition of invasive plants. According to Handayani et al., (2021), ecological risk analysis of potentially invasive species is needed to estimate steps to prevent their spread in the future for ecosystem protection. The impacts of invasive plant invasions can include changes in ecosystem structure, habitat degradation, and reductions in biodiversity (Sunaryo, 2012). Amandari et al., (2023), emphasized the importance of carrying out routine monitoring of invasive plants with the aim of preventing the development of invasive plants in an area. Focusing on risk analysis of invasive plants provides an in-depth understanding of the potential harm that invasive species can cause to local ecosystems (Setiawan et al., 2022).

Due to the many cases of ecosystem damage due to invasive plants, steps in an integrated and sustainable management system are needed to ensure the sustainability of the ecosystem from the threat of invasive plants. The role of research on the composition and structure of invasive plants in West Sumatra conservation areas is not only to understand their impact on biodiversity and ecosystem sustainability, but also as a basis for implementing effective management systems. Steps such as regular monitoring of invasive plant species, risk analysis, and implementation of appropriate control methods are crucial in maintaining the sustainability of ecosystems from the threat of invasive plants. An analysis of the risk of invasive plants in affected areas needs to be carried out to provide in-depth information to determine appropriate and effective actions to overcome their spread. This not only impacts the sustainability of the ecosystem, but also contributes to the conservation of biodiversity. Thus, it is hoped that the implementation of a comprehensive and coordinated management strategy will not only be able to overcome the negative impacts of invasive plants, but also increase public awareness and participation in protecting natural ecosystems.

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